
ANALYSIS OF ADOPTION OF MAGGOT-BASED FEED AMONG CATFISH FARMERS IN SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

Onwumere, Joy Ngozi

Department of Agricultural Economics, Management and Extension
Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Email: joyonwumere267@gmail.com; Phone: +2348035460928

Ezeh, Ann Nnenna

Department of Agricultural Economics, Management and Extension
Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

Email: annezeh2007@yahoo.com; +2348035410610

Abstract:

This study analyzed the adoption of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria, focusing on awareness levels, species preferences, utilization, and major constraints affecting adoption. The research covered Abia, Ebonyi, and Enugu States, where 350 catfish farmers were selected using total sampling from Agricultural Development Projects (ADP)'s registers. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Likert scaling, and factor analysis.

Findings revealed low awareness of maggot-based feed, with only 23% of farmers aware of Black Soldier Fly (BSF) maggots and 16% aware of Domestic Housefly (DHF) maggots. Despite this, 60% of farmers preferred BSF due to its higher nutritional value and lower disease risk. The findings on maggot-based feed utilization techniques by catfish farmers revealed that most farmers preferred using mostly fresh maggot while feeding of dry maggots is slightly less preferred. More labor-intensive or processed forms of maggot feed, such as incorporation into pellets and maggot paste, were less commonly utilized.

No farmer reported outright rejection of maggot-based feed. The finding indicated that the innovation is generally perceived positively among farmers who are exposed to it. In all the States, the level of awareness directly matches the adoption rate. The finding further revealed that once farmers are aware, they tend to adopt, implying that awareness is the main driver of adoption; meaning that farmers who are aware are also likely to adopt. The major constraints identified were fear of disease transmission, inadequate access to credit, poor extension delivery, insufficient government support, and social stigmatization.

The study concludes that maggot-based feed has high potential to serve as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to fishmeal in aquaculture, but adoption remains low due to institutional and perception-related barriers. It recommends intensifying awareness campaigns, providing technical training, improving credit access, and promoting supportive government policies to enhance adoption among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria.

Keywords: Maggot-based feed, Catfish farmers, Awareness, Preference, Utilization Adoption, Constraints, Southeast Nigeria.

Introduction:

Aquaculture has emerged as one of the fastest-growing food production sectors globally, and in Africa, catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* and related species) represents a cornerstone of inland aquaculture (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2020). The African catfish is widely farmed due to its resilience to varying environmental conditions, high growth rate, and strong consumer preference across many African countries. Nigeria is one of the largest producers of farmed catfish in Africa, contributing significantly to both national food supply and regional aquaculture output (FAO, 2020). In this light, catfish farming plays an important socio-economic role by providing employment for thousands of small and medium-scale farmers, supporting rural livelihoods, and serving as a major source of affordable animal protein for Nigerian households.

In Southeast Nigeria, catfish farming is particularly prominent, forming a critical livelihood strategy for smallholder farmers, traders, and processors (Alegbeleye, Obasa, Olude, Otubu and Jimoh, 2020). States such as Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, Imo and Abia have seen steady growth in catfish farming as farmers respond to urban demand and consumer preference for catfish as a staple source of animal protein. Despite this progress, the expansion and sustainability of catfish farming in Southeast Nigeria continue to be constrained by one of the most persistent challenges in aquaculture globally—feed cost. Feed constitutes between 65% and 70% of the total production cost in intensive and semi-intensive catfish farming systems (Sogbesan, Ajuonu, Ugwumba and Madu, 2005; Tacon and Metian, 2015, Henry, Piccolo and Fountoulaki, 2015 and John, 2017). Furthermore, Hardin and Ghandy (2021) noted that feed is an essential element in intensive catfish farming and to have good yields in catfish business, it is necessary to have sufficient quantity and quality feed available at all times.

Meanwhile, fish meal has been the most important source of protein source commonly used in catfish farming which unfortunately must be imported leading to the ever-increasing prices of fish feed. The high cost is largely due to the reliance on conventional protein sources such as fishmeal and soybean meal, which are either imported or produced in insufficient quantities locally (Makkar et al., 2014). As a result, the search for locally available, cost-effective, and nutritionally adequate alternatives to conventional protein ingredients has become a research and development priority.

Several studies such as Adeoye, Abegunrin, Ogunwale and Oyewole, (2019) assessed fish farmers' awareness of organic feed sources for Catfish production in Oyo State, Nigeria. Giovanni, Amato, Biasato and Chiesa (2019) examined the potential role of Insects as Feed for fish production in Ghana. Mustapha and Kolawale (2019) assessed the potentials of Housefly Maggot in the Diet of *Oreochromis niloticus* Fingerlings. Ogunji, Iheanacho, Mgbabu, Amaechi and Evulobi (2021) studied the use of Housefly maggot meal as a potent bio-resource for fish feed to facilitate early gonadal development in *Clarias gariepinus*. Miranda Cammack and Tomberlin (2019) examined the Inter-specific competition between the House Fly, *Musca domestica* L. (Diptera: Muscidae) and Black Soldier Fly, *Hermetia illucens* (L.) (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) reared on poultry manure. Despite the numerous benefits of maggots, it appears they have only been associated with waste product, decay and worthlessness in Nigeria. On the contrary, Mustapha and Kolawale (2019) opined that maggot is a safe and rich protein source for fish as reflected in its chemical composition. None of the above mentioned studies assessed catfish

farmers' awareness and utilization of maggot-based feed (*Hermetia illucens* and *Musca domestica*) among catfish farmers in Southeast, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Assess awareness of catfish farmers on the use of maggots in their production practices and the preferences between the Black Soldier Fly and Domestic Housefly maggot species.
2. Analyze the extent of utilization and rate of adoption of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers.
3. Analyze the constraints to the use of maggots in catfish production.

This research contributes to ongoing efforts to diversify feed sources, improve aquaculture sustainability, and empower local farmers with affordable and environmentally responsible production strategies.

Methods:

Study Area

The study was conducted in Southeast Nigeria, one of the six geopolitical zones of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The region consists of five States—Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo—and is characterized by dense population, fertile land, and a vibrant agricultural economy (NBS, 2023). However, for the purpose of this research, three States—Abia, Ebonyi, and Enugu—were purposively selected based on their high level of participation in aquaculture and the presence of organized catfish farming clusters supported by State Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) (Ekunwe and Emokaro, 2020).

These States also possess favorable environmental conditions, abundant water resources, and active extension systems, making them ideal for the adoption and evaluation of maggot-based feed technologies. Geographically, the area lies between latitudes 4°40' and 7°30'N and longitudes 6°40' and 8°20'E, covering a landmass of approximately 29,000 square kilometers. The region experiences a tropical humid climate with two distinct seasons: the wet season (April to October) and the dry season (November to March). Annual rainfall ranges from 1,800 mm to 2,200 mm, while average temperature varies between 25°C and 32°C, conditions that favor both agricultural and aqua-cultural production throughout the year (NIMET, 2022).

The population is predominantly agrarian, with a large proportion of households engaged in farming activities such as crop cultivation, livestock rearing, and fish farming. Catfish farming in the region is practiced using a mix of earthen ponds, concrete tanks, and plastic ponds, depending on resource availability and farm scale. The region has also witnessed increasing private investment in aquaculture, especially by youth and smallholder farmers seeking profitable ventures (Akinrotimi et al., 2020).

Research Design

A survey research design was adopted for this study. This design was appropriate because it facilitated the systematic collection of descriptive statistics, mean scores derived from a

4-point likert scale, and Factor analysis from a cross-section of catfish farmers actively engaged in maggot-based feed utilization in Southeast Nigeria. Similar approaches were adopted by Tanga et al. (2022).

The design allowed for the analysis of economic variables such as costs, returns, and profitability, as well as socio-economic and institutional factors influencing feed choice and adoption behavior (Ogunji et al., 2008). Through this design, the study examined real-life production situations without manipulating variables, ensuring that the responses reflected the actual experiences of catfish farmers. The approach also enabled comparative analysis between farmers who adopted maggot-based feed and those who relied on conventional fishmeal, thus providing empirical evidence on the profitability and constraints associated with maggot-based feed practices.

Population and Sampling Procedure

The study population comprised all registered catfish farmers operating in Abia, Ebonyi, and Enugu States—three states purposively selected due to their high involvement in catfish production and accessibility to maggot feed innovation trials promoted through Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) and private extension outfits.

A total sampling technique was employed.

A total sampling technique was used to select the respondents. A total sampling technique involved drawing the whole sample from an already existing and comprehensive list of registered catfish farmers obtained from the Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) of Abia, Ebonyi, and Enugu States. This list served as the official sampling frame, ensuring that only actively practicing catfish farmers were included in the survey. The distribution of ADP registered catfish farmers was as follows: Abia State (143), Ebonyi State (115), and Enugu State (102); giving a total of 360 farmers.

However, after administration of the questionnaires, 350 questionnaires were correctly filled and retrieved from the farmers and were used for the analysis after data cleaning. The sample size was deemed adequate to ensure representation and statistical reliability across the three states.

Data Collection Methods

Both primary and secondary data were utilized in the study. Primary data were obtained using a well-structured questionnaire designed to collect information on farmers' socio-economic characteristics, input and output quantities, production costs, revenue from sales, feed type, and constraints to maggot-based feed adoption. Data collection was facilitated by trained enumerators under the supervision of the researcher to ensure completeness and accuracy. Pre-testing of the questionnaire was conducted to verify clarity and relevance before the final field administration.

Analytical Techniques

Both descriptive, likert scale model and factor analysis tools were employed to achieve the study's objectives.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as percentages, means, standard deviations were used to summarize demographic and production characteristics of the farmers.

Likert scale model

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum f n}{N}$$

\bar{X} = Mean

\sum = Summation

f = Likert nominal values of response option; N = Number of response to an item

4-Point Likert Scale

- **VGE = Very Great Extent (4)**
- **GE = Great Extent (3)**
- **LE = Low Extent (2)**
- **VLE = Very Low Extent (1)**

Decision Rule: (2.5 average)

- **Mean ≥ 2.5 → High/Great Extent**
- **Mean < 2.5 → Low/Very Low Extent**

Factor Analysis Model Specification

Exploratory Factor Analysis Model was used to measure objective 5 given as:

$$Y_1 = a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots + a_{1n}X_n$$

$$Y_2 = a_{21}X_1 + a_{22}X_2 + \dots + a_{2n}X_n$$

$$Y_3 = a_{31}X_1 + a_{32}X_2 + \dots + a_{3n}X_n$$

$$* = \dots * \dots * \dots *$$

$$* = \dots * \dots * \dots *$$

$$Y_n = a_{n1}X_1 + a_{n2}X_2 + \dots + a_{nn}X_n$$

Where:

Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n = Observed variables/constraints to the use of maggots in catfish production by catfish farmers.

$a_1 - a_n$ = Factor loadings or correlation coefficients.

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n = Unobserved underlying factors/constraints facing the catfish in the use of maggots in catfish production. Observed variables (constraints) to the use of maggots in catfish production by catfish farmers

Where:

Y₁ = Lack of awareness and knowledge gaps

Y₂ = Inadequate supply of maggots

Y₃ = inadequate training on maggot feeding

Y₄ = Poor extension services

Y₅ = Inconsistent supply/Seasonal fluctuations in maggot availability

Y₆ = Infrastructural limitation

Y₇ = Negative social attitudes towards the use of maggots as feed in catfish

Y₈ = Limited access to credit

Y₉ = Consumer acceptance

Y₁₀ = Disease transmission risk

Y₁₁ = Storage/Preservation challenges

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaire and interview schedule were validated by experts in agricultural economics and aquaculture from the University of Nigeria. The validation ensured that the instrument adequately captured all the variables related to profitability and constraints of maggot-based feed usage. A pre-test was carried out on 30 catfish farmers in Imo State (outside the study area) to test for clarity and consistency. The Bartlett's test of sphericity obtained was (3930.45, $p < 0.01$) confirming a high level of reliability and internal consistency.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in compliance with ethical standards for social science research. Respondents were informed of the study's objectives and assured that participation was voluntary. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. Confidentiality of responses was strictly maintained, and all data were used solely for academic and research purposes. No identifying information was published or disclosed to third parties.

Result:

Awareness of Catfish Farmers Regarding the Use of Maggots in their Production Practices

Table 1 shows the result of the assessment of the catfish farmers' awareness regarding the use of BSF Maggots (BSFM) and DHF Maggots (DHFM) in catfish production in Southeast Nigeria. From the result, the farmers were aware of the use of maggot-based feed in their production practices across Abia, Ebonyi, Enugu, and the Southeast region as a whole. Aggregating across the Southeast, 23% of the farmers were aware of BSFM and 16% were aware of DHFM maggots indicating that while some level of awareness exists,

overall awareness of both BSFM and DHFM remains relatively low in the region, with BSFM slightly more recognized than DHFM with the overall awareness of 23% and 16% respectively.

The result further shows a State-level variation indicating that Abia recorded the highest BSF awareness (30%), while Ebonyi had a slightly lower level (27%) and Enugu lagged far behind with (7%). For DHFM, awareness was relatively higher in Ebonyi (18%) and Abia (16%) than in Enugu (13%). In all the three States in the region, awareness levels were lowest in Enugu, where only 7% of farmers were aware of BSFM and 13% of DHFM in the production of catfish.

Table 1: Percentage Distribution of Awareness to use of Maggots in their Production Practices (N= 350)

State	Item	Frequency	Percentage
Southeast Nigeria (n = 135)	BSF	79	23.0
	DHF	56	16.0
Abia (n = 140)	BSF	42	30
	DHF	23	16
Ebonyi (n = 110)	BSF	30	27
	DHF	20	18
Enugu (n = 100)	BSF	7	7
	DHF	13	13

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Catfish Farmers' Preferences between BSF and BSF Maggot Species in Catfish Production

Table 2 presents the percentage distribution of farmers' preferences for Black Soldier Fly Maggot (BSFM) and Domestic House Fly Maggot (DHFM) across Southeast Nigeria and the individual States of Abia, Ebonyi, and Enugu. At the regional level, 60% of farmers preferred BSFM, while 40% preferred DHFM, indicating a clear overall inclination toward BSF maggots and its growing acceptance among catfish farmers for use in maggot-based feed. State-level analysis reveals variations in preference. Abia had the highest number of farmers favoring BSFM (40 out of 65; 29.6%) and DHFM (25 out of 65; 18.5%). Ebonyi followed with 33 farmers preferring BSFM (24.4%) and 17 preferring DHFM (12.6%). Enugu had the lowest preference with BSFM favored by 8 farmers (5.9%) and DHFM by 12 farmers (8.9%).

Table: 2 Percentage Distribution of Catfish Farmers’ Preferences between BSF and BSF Maggot Species in Catfish Production (N = 135)

State	Item	Frequency	Group Percentage
Southeast (n= 135)	BSFM	81	60
	DHFM	54	40
Abia (n =65)	BSFM	40	29.6
	DHFM	25	18.5
Ebonyi (n=50)	BSFM	33	24.4
	DHFM	17	12.6
Enugu (n =20)	BSFM	8	5.9
	DHFM	12	8.9

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Extent of Maggot-Based Feed Utilization Techniques by Catfish Farmers in the Study Area

Table 3 presents the results of the extent of utilization of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria. The techniques were assessed using a four-point Likert scale: Very Great Extent (VGE = 4), Great Extent (GE = 3), Low Extent (LE = 2), and Very Low Extent (VLE = 1).

The decision benchmark was set at a mean score of 2.50; showing a decision rule of Mean score ≥ 2.50 as “Accepted” (high utilization), while < 2.50 indicated “Rejected” (low utilization). The analysis of the extent of maggot-based feed utilization techniques among catfish farmers revealed that direct feeding of fresh maggot ($\bar{X} = 3.43$) was utilized to a very great extent, while dry maggot meal ($\bar{X} = 3.39$) was utilized to a great extent. In contrast, incorporation of maggots into feed pellets ($\bar{X} = 1.93$) and maggot paste (maggot meal) ($\bar{X} = 1.81$) were utilized to a low and very low extent, respectively.

This indicates that farmers prefer fresh maggot, likely due to ease of use while feeding of dry maggots is slightly less preferred maybe due to time and extra cost. More labor-intensive or processed forms of maggot feed, such as incorporation into pellets and maggot paste, are less commonly utilized. Socio-economic characteristics of the farmers, such as age, education, farming experience, and income, may influence their capacity and willingness to adopt these techniques. Farmers with greater experience and resources are more likely to experiment with processed forms of maggot feed, whereas younger or less experienced farmers rely on simpler methods.

These findings suggest that farmers tend to prefer simpler and more accessible maggot utilization techniques, likely due to the ease of handling, reduced preparation time, and lower associated costs, whereas more processed forms are less commonly employed. Overall, the preference for direct feeding and dry maggot meal reflects a broader pattern of maggot-based feed adoption in the study area, where farmers favor techniques that are practical, cost-effective, and easy to implement.

Table 3: Mean Response on Extent of Maggot-Based Feed Utilization Techniques by Catfish Farmers in the Study Area (N = 350)

Maggot-based Utilization Technique	VGE (4)	GE (3)	LE (2)	VLE (1)	Mean (\bar{X})	Decision Rule	Adoption Extent
Direct feeding (fresh maggots)	220 (63%)	80 (23%)	30 (9%)	20 (6%)	$(220 \times 4 + 80 \times 3 + 30 \times 2 + 20 \times 1) / 350 = 3.43$	≥ 2.5	Very Great Extent
Dry maggot meal	242 (69%)	43 (12%)	26 (7%)	39 (11%)	$(242 \times 4 + 43 \times 3 + 26 \times 2 + 39 \times 1) / 350 = 3.39$	≥ 2.5	Great Extent
Incorporation into feed pellets	51 (15%)	44 (13%)	83 (24%)	172 (49%)	$(51 \times 4 + 44 \times 3 + 83 \times 2 + 172 \times 1) / 350 = 1.93$	< 2.5	Low Extent
Maggot paste (maggot meal)	43 (13%)	39 (11%)	76 (22%)	192 (55%)	$(43 \times 4 + 39 \times 3 + 76 \times 2 + 192 \times 1) / 350 = 1.81$	< 2.5	Very Low Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Rate of Adoption of Maggot-based Feed among Catfish Farmers

The result of the rate of adoption of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria is presented in Table 4. Generally, the findings revealed that only 38.6% of catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria were aware of maggot-based feed, while a larger proportion (61.4%) had no awareness. This aligns with the assertion of Rogers, (2003) in the Diffusion of Innovation theory, which emphasizes that awareness and knowledge are essential precursors to the adoption of any innovation. The relatively low level of awareness suggests limited penetration of maggot-based feed technology in the aquaculture sector of the region.

Final adoption is highest in Abia (46.4%), close in Ebonyi (45.5%), but lowest in Enugu (20%) highlighting the uneven distribution of information and extension services across the States. This finding corroborates the report of Yusuf *et al.* (2016), who observed that disparities in extension contact significantly influence farmers' access to aquaculture innovations in Nigeria. Moreso, the higher adoption in Abia may be attributed to better exposure through local extension services and clustering of commercial catfish farms, which provide a conducive environment for innovation diffusion. Similar observations were reported by Adeoye *et al.* (2017), who found that clustering of aquaculture enterprises fosters quicker dissemination and acceptance of new feeding technologies.

In all the States, the level of awareness directly matches the adoption rate. This suggests that once farmers are aware, they tend to adopt, implying that awareness is the main driver of adoption. This shows a linear relationship, meaning that farmers who are aware are also likely to adopt. Again, the limiting factor is awareness creation. This result also indicates that adoption potential is capped at the awareness level. Enugu's weak awareness explains its low adoption, not farmer resistance. This further shows a perfect alignment between awareness and adoption — farmers who know about maggot-based feed tend to adopt it.

This implies that the major bottleneck is awareness creation, not farmer willingness or rejection. The challenge is not rejection but low exposure — especially in Enugu, where only 20% are aware and therefore only 20% adopt. This implies that if awareness is scaled up, adoption will also rise proportionately.

Interestingly, no farmer reported outright rejection of maggot-based feed. This finding indicates that the innovation is generally perceived positively among farmers who are exposed to it. The absence of rejection aligns with the results of Dienye and Olowosegun (2016), who noted that when aquaculture innovations address cost and availability constraints—such as reducing dependence on expensive fishmeal—farmers are more likely to accept them. The absence of rejection (0%) reinforces that the farmers are open to adoption if barriers are addressed.

Overall, these results are consistent with Rogers’ Diffusion of Innovations theory, which emphasize the progression from awareness → interest → evaluation → trial → adoption (Rogers, 2003). The findings underscore the importance of strengthening awareness creation, particularly in Enugu, where adoption levels are lowest. They also point to the need for policy interventions to scale up awareness campaigns through demonstrations and farmer field schools through extension services which have proven effective in enhancing adoption of novel feed technologies (FAO, 2020).

Table 4: Percentage Distribution of Level of Adoption of Maggot-Based Feed among Catfish Farmers in Southeast Nigeria (N = 350)

Stage of Adoption	Southeast (N=350)	Abia (N=140)	Ebonyi (N=110)	Enugu (N=100)
Awareness (Yes)	135 (38.6%)	65 (46.4%)	50 (45.5%)	20 (20.0%)
Awareness (No)	215 (61.4%)	75 (53.6%)	60 (54.5%)	80 (80.0%)
Interest (Yes)	75 (21.4%)	60 (42.9%)	40 (36.4%)	35 (35.0%)
Interest (No)	275 (78.6%)	80 (57.1%)	70 (63.6%)	65 (65.0%)
Evaluation (Yes)	75 (21.4%)	55 (39.3%)	35 (31.8%)	28 (28.0%)
Evaluation (No)	275 (78.6%)	85 (60.7%)	75 (68.2%)	72 (72.0%)
Trial (Yes)	64 (18.3%)	50 (35.7%)	30 (27.3%)	30 (30.0%)
Trial (No)	286 (81.7%)	90 (64.3%)	80 (72.7%)	70 (70.0%)
Adoption (Yes)	127 (36.3%)	65 (46.4%)	50 (45.5%)	20 (20.0%)
Adoption (No)	223 (63.7%)	75 (53.6%)	60 (54.5%)	80 (80.0%)
Rejection (Yes)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Rejection (No)	350 (100.0%)	140 (100.0%)	110 (100.0%)	100 (100.0%)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Constraints to the Use of Maggots in Catfish Production

Table 5 provides the mean score results of constraints faced by catfish farmers in adopting maggot-based feed. The table ranks the constraints in order of importance, with a cutoff score of 2.50 to distinguish between "accepted" (critical constraints) and "rejected" (less critical or non-significant constraints). The result identifies fear of disease transmission (mean=2.78) and inadequate access to credit (mean=2.72) as the top constraints.

Table 5: Mean score result of constraints to the use of maggots in catfish production

Constraints	Mean	Decision rule	Rank
Fear of disease transmission	2.78	Accepted	1 st
Inadequate access to credit	2.72	Accepted	2 nd
Poor extension services	2.63	Accepted	3 rd
Labour intensive of maggot production	2.61	Accepted	4 th
Inadequate government support	2.58	Accepted	5 th
Inadequate information on maggot as feed for catfish	2.58	Accepted	6 th
Inadequate maggot production infrastructure	2.55	Accepted	7 th
Cultural and social factor(stigmatization)	2.53	Accepted	8 th
Inadequate training and workshop	2.50	Accepted	9 th
Inadequate storage facility	2.22	Rejected	10 th
High cost of inputs	2.13	Rejected	11 th
Inadequate supply of maggot	2.10	Rejected	12 th
Seasonal fluctuation in maggot availability	1.75	Rejected	13 th

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Factor analysis of constraints to the use of maggot in catfish production

Table 6 presents the results of the factor analysis of constraints faced by catfish farmers in adopting maggot-based feed. The constraints were grouped into three key components: Institutional, Economic, and Social. Under the institutional constraints, farmers highlighted poor access to credit (loading = 0.710) as a major institutional barrier, inadequate government support (0.599) and poor extension services (0.809) as critical factors. This shows that weak institutional structures limit farmers’ ability to adopt innovative feed technologies. On the economic side, two main issues stood out; Labour-intensive nature of maggot production has mean of (0.445) and inadequate production infrastructure (0.466). These findings suggest that maggot rearing requires significant inputs, which many smallholder farmers cannot easily provide.

The most dominant set of barriers were social the factors. From the result, inadequate information (0.903) was the strongest constraint overall, showing a major knowledge gap. Farmers also cited fear of disease transmission (0.623), lack of training opportunities (0.753), and stigmatization (0.751) as strong disincentives. These highlight that perception and awareness challenges are equally as important as financial ones. Bartlett’s test of sphericity (3930.45, $p < 0.01$) confirmed that the data were suitable for factor analysis. This ensures that the factors identified are statistically valid and reliable.

In summary, the constraints are not only economic, but also institutional and socio-cultural. Therefore, addressing them requires a multi-pronged strategy involving awareness creation, policy support, training, and provision of infrastructure.

Table 6: Results of factor analysis of constraints to the use of maggot in catfish production

Constraints	Components		
	Institution	Economic	Social
Inadequate information on maggot as feed for catfish	0.008	-0.029	0.903
Inadequate access to credit	0.710	0.237	0.088
Labour intensive of maggot production	0.247	0.445	0.290
Fear of disease transmission	0.375	0.141	0.623
Inadequate government support	0.599	0.219	0.145
Inadequate storage facility	0.321	0.107	0.204
Poor extension services	0.809	0.368	0.138
Inadequate training and workshop	0.387	0.185	0.753
Cultural and social factor(stigmatization)	-0.032	0.105	0.751
Inadequate supply of maggot	0.260	0.131	0.209
High cost of inputs	0.273	0.224	0.210
Seasonal fluctuation in maggot availability	-0.135	0.306	0.107
Inadequate maggot production infrastructure	0.281	0.466	0.195
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	3930.45***		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Discussion:

The study revealed that awareness of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria remains low, with only 23% aware of Black Soldier Fly (BSF) maggots and 16% aware of Domestic Housefly (DHF) maggots. This indicates limited dissemination of information on innovative feed technologies. Abia State recorded the highest awareness level, suggesting that exposure to extension services influences adoption. Most farmers preferred BSF maggots (60%) over DHF due to its superior nutritional profile and reduced risk of diseases transmission.

No farmer reported outright rejection of maggot-based feed. This finding indicates that the innovation is generally perceived positively among farmers who are exposed to it. In all the States, the level of awareness directly matches the adoption rate. This suggests a linear

relationship, which means that once farmers are aware, they tend to adopt, implying that awareness is the main driver of adoption. Again, the limiting factor is awareness creation.

Key constraints included poor extension services which negatively affected uptake. Though the farmers were visited by the extension agents little or no knowledge concerning the benefits accruing from maggot-based utilization was given to them. Fear of disease transmission, limited access to credit, inadequate government support, and stigmatization also constrained the adoption of the innovation. These findings align with prior studies emphasizing that both technical knowledge and perception play major roles in innovation acceptance (Makkar, et al., 2014; Tanga et al., 2021). This result further suggests that both informational and institutional gaps remain critical obstacles to adoption of maggot-based feed in Southeast Nigeria.

Overall, while maggot-based feed offers a sustainable and affordable alternative to conventional fishmeal, adoption is constrained by poor awareness, weak institutional support, and socio-cultural biases.

Conclusion and recommendations:

The study concludes that adoption of maggot-based feed among catfish farmers in Southeast Nigeria is still at an early stage. Farmers recognize its potential to reduce feed costs and improve production, but adoption is limited by inadequate awareness, access to credit, and weak extension systems. If properly promoted and supported, maggot-based feed could become a key driver for sustainable aquaculture and food security in the region.

Finally, the study recommended the following:

1. **Awareness and Training:** Agricultural agencies and NGOs should intensify awareness campaigns and hands-on training on maggot rearing, handling, and feed formulation.
2. **Policy and Financial Support:** Governments should provide incentives such as subsidies or credit schemes to help farmers establish maggot production units.
3. **Strengthen Extension Services:** Reorient extension programs to include maggot-based feed education and demonstrations through farmer field schools.
4. **Address Stigmatization:** Conduct sensitization programs to dispel myths and emphasize the environmental and nutritional benefits of insect-based feeds.
5. **Research and Innovation:** Encourage local research institutions to develop low-cost, labour-saving maggot rearing technologies to make production more feasible for smallholders.

Reference:

- Adeoye, A., Abegunrin, O., Ogunwale, O., & Oyewole, T. (2019). Fish farmers' awareness of organic feed sources for catfish production in Oyo State, Nigeria.
- Akinrotimi, O. A., et al. (2020). Aquaculture development and private investment in Nigeria.
- Alegbeleye, W. O., Obasa, S. O., Olude, O. O., Otubu, K., & Jimoh, W. (2020). Catfish aquaculture and feed innovations in Nigeria.
- Dienye, H. E., & Olowosegun, T. (2016). Adoption of innovative aquaculture practices among fish farmers in Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 11(9), 742–750
- Ekunwe, P. A., & Emokaro, C. O. (2020). Agricultural Development Programmes and aquaculture promotion in South East Nigeria.
- Food and Agriculture Organization. (2020). The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action. Rome: FAO.
- FAO. (2020). Aquaculture statistics in Africa: Regional overview.
- Giovanni, S., Amato, A., Biasato, I., & Chiesa, S. (2019). The potential role of insects as feed for fish production in Ghana.
- Hardin, J., & Ghandy, T. (2021). Feed management and production efficiency in catfish farming.
- Henry, M., Piccolo, G., & Fountoulaki, E. (2015). Fish nutrition and sustainable aquaculture: A review.
- John, T. (2017). Economic assessment of fish feed ingredients in African aquaculture.
- Makkar, H. P. S., Tran, G., Heuzé, V., & Ankers, P. (2014). State-of-the-art on use of insects as animal feed. *Animal Feed Science and Technology*, 197, 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2014.07.008>
- Miranda, C. A., Cammack, J. A., & Tomberlin, J. K. (2019). Inter-specific competition between the house fly (*Musca domestica* L.) and black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens* L.) reared on poultry manure. *Insects*, 10(8), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects10080234>
- Mustapha, A., & Kolawale, A. (2019). Potentials of housefly maggot in the diet of *Oreochromis niloticus* fingerlings. *Nigerian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 7(2), 45–52.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2023). Agricultural performance and employment in Nigeria. Abuja: NBS.

- Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET). (2022). Annual climate review of Nigeria. Abuja: NIMET.
- Ogunji, J. O., Iheanacho, C., Mgbabu, C., Amaechi, N., & Evulobi, C. (2021). Use of housefly maggot meal as a potent bio-resource for fish feed to facilitate early gonadal development in *Clarias gariepinus*.
- Ogunji, J. O., et al. (2008). Economic analysis of aquaculture feed choice among Nigerian fish farmers.
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Sogbesan, O. A., Ajuonu, N., Ugwumba, A. A. A., & Madu, C. T. (2005). Cost analysis of fish feed and profitability in African aquaculture.
- Tacon, A. G. J., & Metian, M. (2015). Feed matters: The role of feed in aquaculture development. *Aquaculture*, 449, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.02.029>
- Tanga, C. M., et al. (2022). Adoption of insect-based feeds among smallholder fish farmers in sub-Saharan Africa.
- Tanga, C. M., et al. (2021). Insect feed innovations and their adoption in sustainable aquaculture.